

NAVIGATING THE TRANSITIONARY POST-PANDEMIC EDUCATIONAL LANDSCAPE: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY OF FILIPINO TEACHERS' EXPERIENCES AND MOTIVATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study attempted to explore the unheard stories of Filipino teachers regarding their experiences and motivations during the shift from online teaching to limited face-to-face instruction in response to the demands of the New Normal. Using purposive sampling, 15 Filipino teachers participated in virtual interviews and answered Google Form surveys. The study employed a phenomenological research design and utilized Colaizzi's seven-step method of data analysis. Findings revealed that the Online Distance Learning Modality (ODLM) encountered several challenges, including unstable internet connectivity, insufficient teaching time, low student attention and participation, lack of technical equipment (gadgets), and the influence of foreign language. Meanwhile, the Modular Distance Learning Modality (MDLM) faced issues related to students' cognitive development, their focus on completing modules, and the creation and revision of learning materials. During the transition to limited face-to-face classes, teachers experienced additional difficulties such as heavier workloads, concerns about students' comprehensive learning, health risks, and constraints on time and mobility. Despite these challenges, their positive experiences and motivations—such as love for the profession, students' eagerness to learn, a strong sense of mission to promote the Filipino language

and literature, and the fulfillment of their dream to become teachers—encouraged them to continue teaching. The researchers believe it is essential to strengthen teachers' motivation to boost morale and enhance dedication to the profession through policies that support the use of modern teaching technologies, provide additional compensation, and ensure physical and mental health care.

Key words: *Filipino, Limited face-to-face teaching, motivation, Online Distance Learning Modality, Modular Distance Learning Modality*

INTRODUCTION

According to the Department of Education (DepEd) in a manual on K to 12 Filipino (Curriculum Guide), the goal of teaching Filipino is to develop students' communicative abilities, reflective/critical thinking, and literary appreciation through reading materials and technology. This aims to foster national identity, cultural literacy, and continuous learning to adapt to the rapid changes happening in the world.

In realizing these K-12 goals, teachers play a significant role as shapers of students' knowledge and skills. According to Ming and Guan (2016), the quality of the education system depends on the competence of teachers. This is supported by Rogayan (2018) who stated that the role of educators encompasses not only the delivery of academic curriculum but also the development of good, aware, and just citizens. This means that Filipino teachers have a significant responsibility in achieving the aforementioned goals.

However, the school year 2019-2020 brought about a sudden change in the world due to the spread of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), which was later declared a pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO). As a result, according to Noval's study (2021), teachers in the country, including Filipino teachers, were compelled to find alternative ways to continue teaching despite the pandemic. In an interview with Leonor Briones, Secretary of the Department of Education (DepEd), she explained that the opening of classes does not mean traditional face-to-face learning. She added that the steps in opening classes are in accordance with the recommendations of the Department of Health (DOH), Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF), and the Office of the President (Malipot, 2020).

With the reopening of the school year, DepEd introduced the "new normal" system. This new normal in education faces various situations, such as the normalization of work from home, distance teaching-learning, online meetings in companies, schools, and others. In fact, the Department of Education (DepEd) is using e-books and modular distance learning for the "new normal" in the field of education (Dhawan, 2020).

In response to the new normal, teachers, including Filipino teachers, have prepared and continue to hone their skills to meet the challenges of teaching using various learning modalities. One of these is the Online Distance Learning Modality (ODLM), where teachers use various platforms to conduct online classes using internet connection.

Another is the Modular Distance Learning Modality (MDLM), where the primary mode of instruction is through modules (Dhawan, 2020).

However, the familiar teaching using online and modular methods for two years is gradually changing as COVID-19 cases in the Philippines decline. In September 2021, the IATF officially approved the first implementation of limited face-to-face classes in areas of the country with low COVID-19 cases.

Limited face-to-face classes refer to a system where 50% of students attend half-day and on "alternate weeks" only. This means that alongside face-to-face classes, students will continue learning through distance learning (Balancio, 2021).

The implementation of limited face-to-face classes was further expanded at the start of 2022 after cases continued to decline in the country. As a result, many teachers have started returning to schools to teach physically to half the number of students.

Due to these changes in the education system in the country, the researcher became interested in exploring the experiences of Filipino teachers to depict the phenomenon related to their challenges and motivations during the new normal in education. This phenomenon is what the researcher wants to examine and has motivated the conduct of this study.

This study is important and timely because it conveys the call of teachers for the support they need from the concerned parties to address the needs in facing the challenges posed by the pandemic, which hinder the delivery of quality education. It will also enlighten parents and students against the misconception that their teachers are not doing anything during these times. Instead, teachers are striving to fulfill their duties as education *frontliners* in their desire to fulfill their sworn duty to provide them with quality education despite the threats posed by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research Objectives

This paper aims to explore the life stories of Filipino teachers from online teaching to the transition towards limited face-to-face teaching, adapting to the demands of the New Normal.

Specifically, it seeks to:

1. Describe the challenges experienced by Filipino teachers during online teaching and the transition to limited face-to-face teaching.
2. Identify the positive experiences of Filipino teachers in using the Modular and Online Distance Learning Modality.
3. Determine the motivations of Filipino teachers in teaching despite the challenges of the pandemic.

The results of this research will serve as a basis for developing policy recommendations or programs that can help Filipino teachers address the challenges of teaching during the New Normal.

METHODOLOGY

To depict the life stories of Filipino teachers from online teaching to the transition towards limited face-to-face teaching while adapting to the demands of the New Normal, this study utilized Husserlian Descriptive Phenomenology and Colaizzi's Seven Steps of Data Analysis. Descriptive phenomenology, established by Edmund Husserl, aims to discover, explore, and explain the meaning or essence of a specific phenomenon under focus (Pereira, 2012). With the help of Colaizzi's seven steps of data analysis, the researcher will be provided with a method to delve into the complex process of interpreting data to discover its prevailing themes.

This study involved fifteen teachers selected through purposive sampling. In this type of sampling, the researcher chooses participants based on the study's requirements (Black, 2010). In selecting the respondents, the researcher used the following inclusion criteria: (a) graduated with a Bachelor's degree in Secondary Education major in Filipino, (b) teaches Filipino at any of the following levels (i.e. JHS, SHS) in the country for the school year 2021-2022, (c) willingly participates in the study without hesitation.

For data collection, the researcher used an interview guide with open-ended questions. To improve the instrument, it was validated by two professors who are experts in the field of Language, Literature, and Research. The first is a Professor II at AFG. Bernardino Memorial Trade School, specializing in Language and Literature. The other is a professor and Research Coordinator at Dr. Yanga's Colleges Inc.

The interview questions were divided into three clusters. The first cluster focuses on the challenges in teaching Filipino during online classes and the transition to limited face-to-face teaching. The second cluster pertains to the positive experiences in teaching using the Modular and Online Distance Learning Modality. The last cluster discusses the motivations in teaching Filipino despite the threat of Covid-19 (New Normal). Here, the researcher asked respondents to narrate their strengths and motivations for continuing their sworn duty. Interviews were conducted online, following health protocols, during their free time, and lasted only 15-30 minutes. Participants who did not opt for an interview were given a week to answer the questionnaire using Google Forms.

To achieve the study's objectives, five teachers participated in interviews, while ten responded through questionnaires using Google Forms. Before the interviews and questionnaire administration, the researcher emphasized ethical considerations by providing a letter for permission. All respondents responded positively. As part of ethical considerations, the respondents' identities were replaced with codes (R1, R2, R3, R4...). Before the interview and questionnaire administration, the purpose of the study was explained to the participants. This was followed by interviews with five teachers, where

their responses were recorded using the audio function of the Zoom Teleconferencing app. The questionnaire was administered for a whole week to ten other teachers.

After data collection, the responses were transcribed. To ensure data privacy, audio recordings of participants were deleted after full transcription. Transcription was followed by data analysis using Colaizzi's (1978) analytic method, which is consistent with Husserl's descriptive phenomenology. The process involves seven steps outlined below: (1) Reading all descriptions (protocols) to gain an understanding of the participants' situation. (2) Extracting meaningful statements. (3) Framing or developing interpretations from meaningful statements. (4) Organizing the developed interpretations according to thematic clusters. (5) Integrating the results into a complete or comprehensive description of the topic under study. (6) Developing a comprehensive or exhaustive description of the phenomenon. (7) Sharing the developed description of their experiences with respondents and soliciting their suggestions or reactions to address any shortcomings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the analysis of the life stories of Filipino teachers, from online teaching to the transition towards limited face-to-face teaching, while adapting to the demands of the New Normal.

The analysis is divided into three thematic clusters: (a) Challenges in Teaching Filipino in the New Normal, (b) Positive Experiences in Teaching Filipino in the New Normal, and (c) Motivations in Teaching Filipino Despite the Threat of Covid-19. The names Respondent 1-15 (R1-R15) are used to protect and maintain their anonymity.

Challenges in Teaching Filipino in the New Normal

The tables present the themes identified and the number of responses for each theme based on the challenges faced by Filipino teachers during the new normal.

Table 1: Challenges in Teaching Filipino using the Online Distance Learning Modality

Theme	Percentage	Direct statement
Hindi maayos na <i>internet connection</i>	12 (80%)	<i>“Karamihan sa mga mag-aaral na nasa online learning ay walang access sa internet, o di kaya naman ay may mahinang koneksiyon, kaya kung may mga aralin sa Filipino lalo na sa gramatika ay hindi sila nakasusunod.” [R1]</i>

Kakulangan ng sapat na oras sa pagtuturo	8 (53.33%)	<i>“Dahil sa limitadong oras at panahon sa pagtuturo nagiging maikli lamang ang nailalaan para maituro ang isang partikular na paksa.[R8]</i>
Kawalan ng atensyon at pakikilahok ng mga mag-aaral	6 (40%)	<i>“Kawalang nang pokus ng mga mag-aaral sa aralin sa kabila nang interaktibong pagtuturo gamit ang iba’t ibang apps.... Nagiging suliranin din ang atensyon ng mga mag-aaral dahil sa kapaligiran na mayroon sila sa kanilang tahanan.” [R11]</i>
Kakulangan sa kagamitang teknikal (gadgets)	3 (20%)	<i>“Ang tanging hamon lamang sa pagtuturo pagdating sa Online Modality ay ang kakulangan ng mga mag-aaral sa paggamit o pagkakaroon ng gadget at internet.”[R2]</i>
Impluwensya ng Banyagang wika	2 (13.33%)	<i>“Limitadong kaalamang pangbokabularyo ng mga mag-aaral dahil sa paglaganap ng kanluraning wika sa social media.” [R6]</i>

Table 1 shows the challenges faced by teachers in teaching Filipino using the Online Distance Learning Modality. From the respondents' responses, the following themes emerged: unreliable internet connection, lack of sufficient teaching time, lack of student attention and participation, lack of technical equipment (gadgets) among students, and the influence of foreign languages.

Of the five themes identified, unreliable internet connection emerged as the primary challenge faced by teachers in teaching Filipino using online learning. Note the following quoted statement:

“There is no guarantee that all students have a stable internet connection. (It is likely that students do not fully understand the lesson due to the robotic delivery of explanations, aside from not being able to connect due to weak signals, which leads to misunderstandings in the use of language or grammar)” [R1]

This result aligns with Noval's study (2021), which also found unreliable internet connection to be a leading problem. This is not surprising, as education in the new normal relies heavily on technology. This means that the internet, which powers many of its tools, is crucial. According to Noval's (2021) study, as cited by the World Bank, in 2020, most students struggled to access online learning (Ali & Kaur, 2020).

According to Friedman (2020), technical problems are inevitable in online classes. Technical issues can affect student learning because they may miss crucial parts of the discussion (Ryan, 2020). Toquero's study (2021) further adds that slow or unreliable internet, connection costs, technophobia, lack of 21st-century technological skills, and lack of devices are just some of the obstacles to distance learning instruction. Therefore, it is crucial to improve infrastructure that can help solve and improve the quality of internet connection in the country, especially now that flexible learning is part of the education system and new normal teaching.

The second theme with the most responses is the lack of sufficient teaching time. Note the following quoted statement:

“Currently, the internet is a major problem in student learning, and classes are only held once a week. Because of this, there is limited time to provide activities that can deepen and bring to life the lessons on grammar.” [R3]

The Department of Education (DepEd) reminded that students participating in online distance learning (ODL) should only spend a maximum of one to four hours after the department issued a memorandum. According to DepEd Undersecretary for Curriculum and Instruction Diosdado San Antonio, the Memorandum DM-CI-2020-00162, which contains proposed strategies to guide teachers and students in the implementation of distance learning delivery modalities (DLDM), must be followed. Notably, the order allows only up to 2 hours for Grades 6 to 8. Meanwhile, 4 hours is the maximum recommended screen time for students in Grades 9 to 12: up to 2 hours in the morning and up to 2 hours in the afternoon.

This order was immediately implemented by Filipino teachers, but as the study reveals, if the focus is on the quality of what students learn, respondents are confident that it is insufficient. This has become a challenge for respondents because the nature of Filipino, especially literature, is extensive. Therefore, it also requires a long learning time. Moreover, due to slow internet connections, teachers have less time to teach.

The third theme identified in the analysis is the lack of student attention and participation. One of the respondents stated:

“First is the lack of student focus on the lesson despite interactive teaching using various apps.” [R7]

In Salino et al.'s research (2018), some factors affecting students' lack of interest and focus are the influence of online games, which results in laziness in attending classes. It also stated that their focus on learning is affected by family problems, personal problems, and the simultaneous submission of projects with the same deadline, which significantly impacts their interest in learning.

Along with the lack of interest, the theme of lack of technical equipment (gadgets) among students also emerged from the analysis of the study. Note the following explicit statement by the respondent:

“Lack of technical equipment and weak internet connection on the part of teachers, especially students. This is a major obstacle to students' deeper understanding of language lessons.” [R10]

This problem is similar to what emerged in Noval's study (2021), where the lack of technical support for students had a significant impact. It can be inferred from the statement that the lack of gadgets is a major obstacle for participants because it is crucial for communication and discussion of lessons. Ali and Kaur (2020) mentioned that most students rely on their parents'/guardians' cell phones and only have access based on a set time. Lapada and colleagues (2020) also stated that teachers are willing to transition to distance learning education, but they feel the challenges due to the lack of facilities, equipment, and capacity building in distance learning. This confirms what the participants expressed, that teaching during the pandemic is more challenging because many changes have occurred in the teaching process, almost all of which rely on internet connectivity and other virtual methods. It would also be beneficial to allocate additional funds to provide gadgets and learning materials to students who lack the capacity to meet these needs.

The emergence of the theme of the influence of foreign languages as a challenge faced by teachers in teaching Filipino is noteworthy.

“One of the problems is the students' limited vocabulary knowledge due to the prevalence of Western culture (foreign languages).” [R9]

It can be inferred from this that even before the arrival of modern times, learning the Filipino language has been affected in many aspects. According to the Glocalism: Journal of Culture, Politics and Innovation (Edward, 2018), globalization is widespread, with many foreign works becoming popular among Filipinos. Along with this inclination, there is a forgetting of one's own culture, language, and literature. This result means that even in the new normal, there is no difference, and it remains a problem in many Filipino classes.

Table 2: Challenges in Teaching Filipino Using the Modular Distance Learning Modality

Theme	Percentage	Direct statement
Kakulangan sa pagkatuto at kapuna-punang awtput ng mga mag-aaral	13 (86.67%)	“Ang mga mag-aaral na pumili sa modular learning ay gumagamit ng SELF LEARNING MODULE dahil wala silang access ss internet, at

		<i>dahil self-learning ito at self-paced kung ano lamang ang kanilang pagkaunawa sa nasa nilalaman ng module ay pinag-uubra na nila, kaya kapuna-puna sa mga output na may kakulangan sa pagkatuto.” [R1]</i>
Kawalan ng pokus sa pagsagot sa modyul	4 (26.67%)	<i>“Karamihan sa mga mag-aaral ay hindi na binabasang mabuti ang mga teksto. Kapag nakitang mahaba ang akda, babasahin na lamang ang mga tanong at hahanapin ang kasagutan nito ng kahit hindi na buong nauunawaan ang nilalaman.” [R7]</i>
Pagbuo at pagwawasto ng modyul	3 (20%)	<i>“Nahihirapan sa paggawa dahil mahaban ang proseso gayon din ang agarang interaksyon at kagyat na pagwawasto sa mga maling sagot ng mag-aaral.” [R15]</i>

Table 2 presents the challenges faced by teachers in teaching Filipino using the Modular Distance Learning Modality. From the respondents' answers, the following themes emerged: insufficient learning and unsatisfactory student output; lack of focus in answering the module; and module creation and correction.

The dominant theme was insufficient learning and unsatisfactory student output. Note the following quoted statement:

“Aside from late submissions of module assignments; copy-paste answers; some students don't read the module, so their answers are wrong... we're often not sure if students fully understand the content of the literature or if they even read the entire work, or if they just looked for the answers to the questions.” [R8]

The researcher observed a strong correlation between this problem and the second theme, lack of focus in answering the module. The low interest shown by students in answering the module results in unsatisfactory output, leading to incomplete learning. Kofahi et al. (2004) believe that the lack of interaction between the teacher and the student is a major problem that can lead to a deficiency in what the student learns, even when self-learning modules are used. Communication or interaction between the teacher and the student is still important to help, especially those students who have no one to guide them in answering the module.

Students really struggle with the module, especially if there's no one to guide them in answering, according to the Filipino teachers who were respondents in this study.

“It's difficult for children nowadays; they don't have anyone at home to help them with their modules. Even if they have someone to help, that person's knowledge of the specific lesson is insufficient. That's why many children find it difficult to learn using modular learning.” [R11]

The theme of module creation and correction is also among the challenges faced by teachers. As stated by the respondent below:

“Creating modules requires meticulous work, so some lessons haven't been discussed yet because the modules to be used aren't ready yet. I also have difficulty with immediate interaction and immediate correction of students' wrong answers.” [R15]

In Noval's study (2021), it is stated that it is not easy for teachers to continue teaching, especially in creating, collecting, and correcting modules. This added to the teachers' paperwork, especially since they also have online classes. Lapada and colleagues (2020) mentioned that teachers, students, and schools are still adjusting to distance learning education. Many institutions of Higher Education, private or state colleges and universities, are not yet ready for the implementation of the online system (Toquero, 2020)

Table 3: Challenges in Teaching Filipino During the Transition to Limited Face-to-Face Learning

Theme	Percentage	Direct statement
Mas mabigat na trabaho sa pagtuturo	7 (46.67%)	<i>“sa aking palagay ay mas nadagdagan pa aking mga gawain sapagkat kami ngayon ay hahawak ng tatlong klase na may tatlong pamamaraan ng pagtuturo at pagkatuto, dahil iba-iba ang piniling modality ng mgam mag-aaral.” [R4]</i>
Kasiguraduhan sa ganap na pagkatuto ng mga mag-aaral	4 (26.67%)	<i>“isang hamon sa pagbalik ng face-to-face ay hindi ganoon kalalim na pagkatuto sa mga naunang paksang tinalakay kung kaya, marapat na ang mga guro lalo na sa Filipino ay gawin itong pagkakataon upang maisagawa ang iba't ibang gawaing pampagkatuto sa pagtalakay ng Wika at panitikan.” [R5]</i>

Banta sa kalusugan	3 (20%)	<i>“Nakatatakot isipin na baka dumating ang panahon na muling tumaas ang kaso ng COVID-19 at may mga estudyante akong pumapasok sa limited f2f class...”</i> [R13]
Limitadong oras at paggalaw	2 (13.33%)	<i>“limitadong mag-aaral, oras, at paggalaw para ituro ang wika at panitikan.”</i> [R5]

Table 3 presents the challenges faced by Filipino teachers during the transition to limited face-to-face learning. The responses of the teachers revealed four main themes: heavier workload in teaching; ensuring complete learning of students; health risks; and limited time and movement.

The most prominent theme was the heavier workload in teaching. This was explicitly revealed by the respondents through the following quoted statement:

“As a teacher, I think my workload has increased because not everyone can go back to class yet. Some students still have to answer printed modules, relying on themselves, and those who attend online classes have the chance to listen to the teacher's lessons and explanations. As for those who will be part of LF2F, I think they will be able to focus more on their lessons because of their eagerness to return to school like before.” [R4]

DepEd's issuance of RM No. 110, s. 2022 instructed teachers under limited face-to-face learning to continue the chosen learning modality of the students. This resulted in teachers having to implement different modalities in their teaching. This explains the complaints of some respondents that teaching has become heavier for them because of the multiple approaches they need to employ to ensure student learning. Since not all students can yet return to physical classes, this remains a challenge for teachers, particularly in teaching Filipino, where language and literature need to be taught.

Another theme that emerged from the analysis was the assurance of complete learning for students. This was expressed through the following quoted statement:

“Based on the mentioned problems in the online modality in learning language and literature, a challenge upon returning to face-to-face is the lack of depth in learning the previous topics discussed. Therefore, teachers, especially in Filipino, should take this opportunity to implement various learning activities in discussing language and literature.” [R5]

This theme highlights the logical connection between student learning from online learning to limited face-to-face learning. The researcher realized that it is difficult for students to fully learn with the sudden change in the teaching system. The respondents acknowledged that online learning did not provide complete learning, making it a major

challenge for teachers in limited face-to-face learning to restore the quality and substance of Filipino instruction.

The health risk also emerged as a prominent theme among the challenges during the transition to limited face-to-face learning. One respondent stated:

“It’s scary to think that there might come a time when COVID-19 cases rise again, and I have students attending limited f2f classes... this is a real threat, how can we ensure that no child gets sick.” [R13]

Their responses reveal their concern for their health, but they continue to persevere in teaching for the benefit of their families and students. Therefore, it is important to launch programs or activities that will promote ensuring the safety of teachers and students inside the school.

Toquero (2020) mentioned that strengthening educational planning and implementing health measures will provide students and stakeholders with the opportunity to continue learning while preventing the spread of the virus (Toquero, 2020). Many lives around the world have changed because of COVID-19. It has created fear, trauma, depression, and anxiety, especially for those who have lost loved ones (Talidong and Toquero, 2020). These studies prove that fear and anxiety for their health are part of the challenges faced by teachers.

Ensuring the safety of teachers and students is related to the last theme that emerged from the analysis. The theme of limited time and movement as a challenge in teaching during the transition to limited face-to-face classes is a direct solution to ensure the safety of those involved.

Some respondents who expressed: “limited students, time, and movement to teach language and literature.” as a problem, imply that it is not easy to teach in physical classes that are full of limitations. However, if you think about it, it is difficult for this problem to disappear because the Philippines remains under a pandemic.

Positive Experiences in Teaching Filipino in the New Normal

The tables presented the themes that emerged and the number of responses for each theme based on the positive experiences of Filipino teachers during the pandemic.

Table 4: Positive Experiences in Teaching Filipino Using Online and Modular Distance Learning Modality (Blended Learning Modality)

Theme	Percentage	Direct statement
Pagtuklas sa makabagong pamamaraan sa pagtuturo	8 (53.33%)	<i>“Ang masayang bahagi ng online learning modality ay ang pagkatuto</i>

		<i>ng mga makabagong pamaraan ng pagtuturo at pagkatuto... masarap din sa pakiramdam kapag nagagamit namin ang mga online games sa pagtuturo at pagkatuto. Mas natuto ang guro sa Filipino na gumamit ng mga interaktibong kagamitan sa pagtuturo gaya ng Kahoot, mentimeter atbp” [R1R3R5]</i>
Nakapagpapatuloy pa rin ang edukasyon	5 (33.33%)	<i>“Masaya dahil maipagpapatuloy pa rin ang pagtuturo kahit na virtually lang kami nagkikita ng mga mag-aaral... Mapalad kaming mga gurong may hanap-buhay pa rin sa kabila ng pandemya, isa itong realisasyon at motibasyon para ipagpatuloy ang tungkulin.” [R6, R9]</i>
Mabilis matukoy ang mga desididong matuto sa kabila ng hamon	4 (26.67%)	<i>“Madaling makilala ang mga mag-aaral na desididong mag-aral at aktibo sa klase.... Humahanga ako sa mga mag-aaral na talagang ipinakita pa rin ang kanilang sipag at tiyaga sa pag-aaral kahit hindi nakikita at nakakausap ang guro ng madalas.” [R7]</i>

Table 4 highlights the positive experiences of teachers in teaching Filipino using the Blended Learning Modality. From the respondents' answers, the following themes emerged: discovering innovative teaching methods, the continuity of education, and the ability to quickly identify those who are determined to learn despite the challenges.

Many respondents stated that the Blended Learning Modality (Online and Modular) helped them discover many innovative teaching methods. This led to the theme of discovering innovative teaching methods. Note the following quoted statement:

“The integration of Filipino lessons with online games and other social media platforms has brought joy not only to students but also to teachers.” [R3]

“Teaching became fun and easier for me because of the Online Learning Modality because it made lesson preparation and teaching faster through the internet and directly showing or letting students watch presentations or videos embedded in each lesson.” [R7]

This is not surprising because since classes opened under the pandemic, many teachers have been forced to find different ways to ensure student learning. According to Felonia (2021), for teaching strategies and tools to be effective during the pandemic, they must focus on certain things. These are the things to consider when choosing the teaching method to be used for students. When given proper attention, the learning process for students will be easier and smoother, and it can be a bridge to making the teacher's strategies more effective.

The first theme that emerged is simply an indication that for many teachers, discovering many innovative teaching methods using technology is a great opportunity. It reflects a joyful experience for them.

The second theme that emerged is the continuity of education. Note the following quoted statement:

"It's nice because we can still continue teaching even if we only see the students virtually... it opened our minds more to the changes that might happen because of the pandemic." [R6, R9]

It can be inferred from this that it is a big deal for teachers that education is still continuing despite the pandemic. According to Ordones (2020), the reopening of classes, even with serious health concerns, can provide many teachers with the opportunity to earn money and continue to support their families. This statement shows why teaching in the midst of the pandemic continues to be a positive experience for teachers.

From the analysis, the theme of quickly identifying those who are determined to learn despite the challenges also emerged as a positive experience for teachers during the teaching period in the midst of the pandemic. This can be seen in the following quoted statement:

"I am impressed by the students who really showed their diligence and perseverance in learning even if they don't see and talk to the teacher often... I got to know the children better in terms of behavior and abilities." [R7]

It can be inferred from this that teachers are happy to see the efforts of their students despite the challenges of the pandemic. Here, teachers can quickly identify which students are diligent in their studies.

Table 5: Positive Experiences in Teaching Filipino During the Transition to Limited Face-to-Face Learning

Theme	Percentage	Direct statement
Makitang muli nang personal ang mga mag-aaral	11 (73.33%)	<i>“Masaya kasi sa halos dalawang taon na hindi kami nagkikita-kita, dito ay nakita na naming ang isa’t isa. Mas naging buo ang relasyon sa pagitan ng guro at mag-aaral.” [R15]</i>
Kasabikan ng mga mag-aaral	7 (46.67%)	<i>“Natutuwa ako na makita na lahat sila ay sabik na magbalik-eskuwela dahil dito mas nagaagnahan akong magturo.” [R13]</i>

Table 5 presents the positive experiences of teachers in teaching Filipino during the transition to limited face-to-face learning. From the responses of the participants, two themes emerged: seeing students again in person and the eagerness of the students.

From the quoted statement below, we can identify the first theme that emerged from the analysis regarding the joyful experiences of teachers in teaching in limited face-to-face classes.

“I am happy because after almost two years of not seeing each other, we can finally see one another. The relationship between the teacher and the students has become stronger.” [R15]

After a long time spent at home, the reopening of classes became a significant source of joy for both teachers and students. This was made possible by President Rodrigo Duterte's approval to conduct limited face-to-face classes.

In September 2021, the IATF officially approved the first implementation of limited face-to-face classes in areas of the country with low COVID-19 case numbers. The limited face-to-face class system allows 50% of students to attend half-day and "alternate weeks" only. This means that, alongside face-to-face classes, students will continue their studies through distance learning (Balancio, 2021).

Related to the previous theme, another positive experience for teachers participating in limited face-to-face teaching was the emerging theme of students' eagerness. Note the following quoted statement:

“I am pleased to see that they are all excited to return to school because it motivates me to teach more.” [R13]

Motivations in Teaching Filipino Despite the Threat of Covid-19

Table 6 presents the themes that emerged based on the motivations of the participants in teaching Filipino despite the threat of COVID-19.

Theme	Percentage	Direct statement
Pagmamahal sa sinumpaang tungkulin	6 (40%)	<i>“Tungkulin itong dapat gampanan nang buong katapatan. Ngayon kami higit na kailangan ng mga mag-aaral.” [R5]</i>
Interes ng mga mag-aaral na matuto sa kabila ng hamon	4 (26.67%)	<i>“Ang pagiging masigasig ng aking mga mag-aaral ang pangunahing dahilan kung bakit sa kabila ng napakaraming hamong dulot ng pandemya ay patuloy pa rin tayo sa pagsusulong ng edukasyon...para sa bayan, para sa bata.” [R7]</i>
Mamulat ang kabataan sa kariktan at sining ng Wika at Panitikan	3 (20%)	<i>“Gusto ko na mamulat ang mga mag-aaral sa ganda at singing ng wika at panitikan ng kaniyang sariling bayan na kaugnay ng pagmamahal niya sa bayan” [R3]</i>
Pangarap ang pagiging isang guro	2 (13.33%)	<i>“Mula noong nag-aaral pa lang ako hanggang ngayong ako ay 13 taon na sa aking pagiging guro, isa lang ang motibasyong aking sinasabuhay, I AM BORN TO TEACH... kahit napapagod, kahit nahihirapan at kahit halos bumitaw na ay babangon pa rin at iisipin ang mga batang naghihintay na maturuan at mabahaginan ng kaalaman. ISINILANG AKONG MAGING GURO, MAMATAY AKONG GURO...Salamat sa Panginoon at dinala ako sa ganitong propesyon at bokasyon.” [R1]</i>

Table 6 highlights the motivations of participants in teaching Filipino despite the threat of COVID-19. Four key themes emerged from the respondents' answers: love for their

sworn duty, students' interest in learning despite challenges, awakening youth to the beauty and artistry of language and literature, and the dream of being a teacher.

The theme of love for sworn duty emerged as the most prominent. Respondents openly expressed this sentiment:

“My only motivation for continuing to teach is that, aside from it being my sworn duty, I have seen the importance of language and literature during this pandemic.” [R10]

“This is a duty that should be fulfilled with utmost sincerity. We are fortunate teachers who still have jobs despite the pandemic. This is a realization and motivation for us to continue our duty. Now, we are needed more than ever by the students.” [R5]

“First and foremost, I love and enjoy teaching.” [R6]

These responses reveal the teachers' strong desire and commitment to teaching, demonstrating that no virus can hinder their passion for their profession. According to Galvez (2018), motivation plays a crucial role in shaping behavior in any organization. It is a need, a desire that organizes and guides members towards a common goal. For teachers, their love for their duty directly shapes their desire to continue teaching, despite the significant threat the pandemic poses to their health.

Noval's (2021) study, drawing on the work of Dornyei and Ushioda (cited in Han and Yin, 2016), emphasized two dimensions of teacher motivation: motivation to teach and motivation to stay in the profession. The teachers' love for their sworn duty results in their continued commitment to their profession.

Another theme identified in the analysis was the students' interest in learning despite challenges. Consider this quoted statement:

“The enthusiasm of my students is the main reason why, despite the many challenges caused by the pandemic, we continue to promote education... for the country, for the children.” [R7]

This suggests that whenever teachers feel discouraged, their students' eagerness to learn gives them the strength to persevere. This characteristic of teachers reflects the Filipino trait of being willing to dedicate themselves to others. This theme is evident in the teachers' willingness to do everything they can to provide their students with a quality education.

The analysis also revealed the theme of awakening youth to the beauty and artistry of language and literature. Respondents expressed this sentiment directly:

“I want my students to be aware of the beauty and artistry of the language and literature of their own country, which is linked to their love for the nation.” [R3]

As Filipino teachers, they naturally have a strong sense of care and love for the national language. According to Delacruz (2018), Filipino teachers are patriotic because they bear the great responsibility of reviving and preserving the culture and identity of the Philippines. Therefore, this statement clearly shows that the motivation of a Filipino teacher is their desire to awaken young people to the value and artistry of the Filipino language and literature.

A final motivating factor for teachers to continue teaching despite the threat of the pandemic is the dream of being a teacher. Respondents expressed this joyously:

“From the time I was a student to now, 13 years into my teaching career, I have only lived by one motivation: I AM BORN TO TEACH... It is difficult to be a teacher, especially now in the new normal. Many changes have occurred in the way we teach, but whenever I say to myself, 'I am Born to Teach,' even when I am tired, even when I am struggling, and even when I am about to give up, I will still get up and think about the children who are waiting to be taught and share knowledge. As the saying goes, you may get tired, but you will not give up. You may cry, but you will still laugh... You may struggle, but you will continue because I WAS BORN TO BE A TEACHER, I WILL DIE A TEACHER... Thank you, Lord, for bringing me to this profession and vocation.” [R1]

In Börü's (2018) study, he discussed two main factors in teacher motivation: internal and external motivation resources. In the current study, the themes of love for sworn duty and the dream of being a teacher fall under internal motivation resources, while awakening youth to the beauty and artistry of language and literature and students' interest in learning despite challenges can be categorized as external motivation resources. These findings suggest that, even in the face of a pandemic, the teaching profession in the country remains strong and dedicated to teaching.

Conclusions

This research explored the experiences of Filipino teachers, tracing their journey from online instruction to the transition towards limited face-to-face learning while navigating the demands of the New Normal. It delved into the challenges encountered, positive experiences, and motivations of the respondents in teaching Filipino amidst the ever-changing educational landscape brought about by the pandemic. The researcher believes that this study can serve as a valuable foundation for developing policy recommendations or programs to address these challenges and continue to promote high-quality education.

The analysis revealed that Filipino teachers, when utilizing the Online Distance Learning Modality (ODLM), face significant challenges related to unreliable internet connectivity, insufficient teaching time, lack of student attention and engagement, inadequate access to technological equipment (gadgets), and the influence of foreign languages.

In implementing the Modular Distance Learning Modality (MDLM), teachers encountered challenges related to insufficient learning and unsatisfactory student output, lack of student focus in completing modules, and difficulties in creating and correcting modules.

Respondents also highlighted challenges faced during the transition to limited face-to-face instruction. They reported a heavier workload due to the need to implement diverse modalities (e.g., ODLM, MDLM, Limited face-to-face) within a single section to ensure student learning. As full return to physical classrooms remains impractical, this challenge persists. Other challenges identified for Filipino teachers include ensuring complete student learning, health risks associated with the pandemic, and limited time and movement within the classroom.

Despite these challenges, the researcher found that positive experiences prevailed for teachers despite the numerous trials they faced. Positive experiences in utilizing ODLM and MDLM (Blended Learning) included discovering innovative teaching methods, the continuation of education, and the ability to quickly identify students who are determined to learn despite the challenges. The transition to limited face-to-face learning was also viewed as a positive experience for Filipino teachers, allowing them to see their students in person again and witness the students' eagerness to return to school.

Alongside these positive experiences, respondents also shared their motivations for continuing to teach despite the challenges. This aligns with the principles of Self-Determination Theory. Motivations for Filipino teachers included their love for their sworn duty, their students' interest in learning despite challenges, their mission to awaken young people to the beauty and artistry of language and literature, and their lifelong dream of being a teacher.

Strengthening these motivations is crucial for teachers to continue their profession. The researcher believes that understanding their motivations is essential for boosting their morale and dedication to their chosen profession. This can be achieved through policies related to the use of innovative teaching technologies, additional compensation, and initiatives to safeguard physical and mental well-being.

Recommendations

To address the primary challenge of slow internet connectivity faced by Filipino teachers using ODLM, the researcher recommends that DepEd and CHED allocate additional funds for internet allowances for teachers. This initiative could be expanded through collaboration with Local Government Units (LGUs) to provide internet modems to all teachers, both public and private, ensuring that they do not have to rely on their own resources. The researcher believes that slow internet speeds are a contributing factor to the challenge of insufficient teaching time. Providing teachers with these resources would allow them to maximize their time for instruction. To address the lack of gadgets and learning resources, the researcher recommends that LGUs nationwide, in collaboration with the National Government through DepEd/CHED, expand and make mandatory the distribution of laptops, tablets, or other gadgets to students in greater need. This response could also address the challenge of lack of focus and attention among students attending online classes.

To tackle the primary challenge of insufficient learning and unsatisfactory student output in MDLM, the researcher recommends that teachers or schools ensure that each student has a reliable and supportive individual at home to assist them with their studies. Regular home visits are also recommended to confirm the availability of support within the student's household. Additionally, capacity building programs for teachers in developing 21st-century technological skills are suggested to alleviate the difficulties teachers face in creating, collecting, and correcting modules.

Regarding the primary challenges faced by teachers during the transition to limited face-to-face instruction, the researcher recommends that each Filipino department in schools develop a system and policy where the number of teachers is divided according to the number of modalities or teaching methods. There would be teachers solely focused on ODLM, others on MDLM, and others on limited face-to-face instruction. The implementation of strict safety protocols to prevent the spread of COVID-19 should also be formalized through policy.

As this study only included fifteen Filipino teachers, it is recommended that similar studies be conducted with a larger sample size. The study should also consider other subjects and aspects of teaching in the new normal education system.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research hinges on informed consent, ensuring participants fully understand the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw. Confidentiality and anonymity are crucial, protecting participant identities through techniques like pseudonyms and secure data storage. Researcher reflexivity acknowledges inherent subjectivity and potential biases, requiring self-reflection and critical examination of one's influence on the research process. Navigating power dynamics demands respect and equitable relationships, avoiding exploitation or coercion. Finally, responsible dissemination ensures accurate and ethical presentation of findings, avoiding misrepresentation or harm to participants, and adhering strictly to the purposes outlined in the consent form.

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